

Digitalisation of Wind Lidar

Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG5 presentation

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The Working Group members

How we started (in 2022)

The Working Group's Original Format

Objectives:

1. Identify the **business cases for digitalisation** throughout the lifecycle of a wind lidar and the lifecycle of a wind farm
2. Identify **existing solutions and highlight gaps**
3. Provide **working demonstrations of digitalisation** in practice, including a wind lidar ontology and data processing based on open-source tools.

Group approach:

The group will meet online every month to discuss general progress and realign.

Deliverables and timeframe:

1. Support the publishing of a first version of **a wind lidar ontology** (a structured glossary of wind lidar terms) during 2022
→ Working Group 7
2. Demonstrate a **wind lidar data processing chain** based on open source tools, including the e-WindLidar data format, during 2023
3. Additional **objectives might be added in the future**, for example aligned with the activities of Task 43.

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Digitalisation:

The organisational and industry-wide use of data and digital technologies to improve efficiency, create insights, and develop products and services.

Huh?

Digitalisation in the context of “Large Scale Deployment”

7

Wind lidar manufacturers
How do you build and manage 10x as many wind lidar, without having to build a 10x larger company?

Data analysts

How do you learn from the data from 10x as many wind lidar, without having 10x as many experts to employ?

Wind farm operators

How do you manage a fleet of 100+ wind lidar and integrate their data into daily operations?

Our journey

A curated collection of lidar data samples (2023)

A wind data analyst wants to prepare their processes to work with data from a new type of wind lidar,

But... they can't get data samples.

So... we put together a curated set of data samples

Data samples							
ID	Device	Operating mode	Format	Source	Link to data	Description	License
0	ZX300	VAD	Manufacturer's own	Data provided by ZX Lidars	drive.google.com	Data are direct from the wind lidar and have not been modified.	no license provided
1	WindCube V1	DBS	Manufacturer's own	Data provided by CU Boulder through A2e	a2e.energy.gov	According to the metadata, data files are direct from the wind lidar and have not been modified.	CC0 Public DomLinkin Dedication
2	WindCube V2.1	DBS	Manufacturer's own	Data provided by NREL through A2e	a2e.energy.gov	According to the metadata, data files are direct from the wind lidar and have not been modified.	CC0 Public DomLinkin Dedication
3	WindCube 200s	3-D scanning	Manufacturer's own	Data provided by UTD through A2e	a2e.energy.gov	According to the metadata, data files are direct from the wind lidar and have not been modified.	CC0 Public DomLinkin Dedication
4	Halo XR	3-D scanning	Manufacturer's own	Data provided by PNNL through A2e	a2e.energy.gov	According to the metadata, data files are direct from the wind lidar and have not been modified.	CC0 Public DomLinkin Dedication
						According to the	

<https://github.com/IEAWindTask52/LidarDataSamples>

A data exchange concept (2023 -)

A wind data analyst wants to use wind lidar data from a third party in a wind resource assessment. The IEA Wind Task 43 data model helps with data transfer.

But... The data model separated data and metadata

So... IEA Wind Task 43 was already working on it.

https://github.com/IEA-Task-43/digital_wra_data_standard

Where we are now

What is digitalisation?

It is not a magic solution to everything

Photo by [Shayna Douglas](#) on [Unsplash](#)

It's just another tool

Photo by [Carlos Felipe Ramírez Mesa](#) on [Unsplash](#)

How to choose the right tool for the job

1. Know your customer
2. Understand their goals
3. Know the constraints
4. Have a definition of success

We looked at real and future user stories

People

Tasks

Goals

Obstacles

Business cases

Where can digitalisation really make a difference?

We collected over 30 user stories

⚡ Database of wind lidar user stories ...

📄 Design 5

on land offshore

Now

A wind lidar product owner specifying a new product

on land offshore

Now

A wind lidar designer creating a new wind lidar design

on land offshore

Now

A wind lidar designer seeks to

📄 Manufacturing 5

Now

A wind lidar manufacturing technician needs to validate components for use in a wind lidar

on land offshore

Now

A wind lidar designer seeks to improve an existing design

on land offshore

Now

A wind lidar business manager

📄 Lidar

on land

Now

A lidar verify 200m

on land

Now

A data verific require

on land

Now

The results

Wind lidar manufacturers

How do you build and manage 10x as many wind lidar, without having to build a 10x larger company?

Wind lidar Widget manufacturers
How do you build and manage 10x as many widgets ~~wind lidar~~, without having to build a 10x larger company?

A photograph of a modern industrial manufacturing facility. The scene is dominated by several large, orange robotic arms (likely KUKA) positioned along a production line. The robots are mounted on metal frames and are in various stages of operation. The background shows a well-lit factory floor with various equipment, including conveyor belts, metal structures, and safety railings. The overall atmosphere is one of a busy, high-tech manufacturing environment.

Wind lidar Widget manufacturers
How do you build and manage 10x as many widgets ~~wind lidar~~, without having to build a 10x larger company?

→ This is a typical manufacturing challenge

Data analysts

How do you learn from the data from 10x as many wind lidar, without having 10x as many experts to employ?

Data analysts

How do you learn from the data from 10x as many customers with lidar, without employing 10x as many analysts?

Data analysts

How do you learn from the data from 10x as many customers ~~wind-lidar~~, without employing 10x as many analysts?

→ This is a typical data analytics challenge

Wind farm operators

How do you manage a fleet of 100+ wind lidar and integrate their data into daily operations?

Wind farm operators

How do you manage a fleet of 100+ sensors ~~wind lidar~~ and integrate their data into daily operations?

Wind farm operators

How do you manage a fleet of 100+ sensors ~~wind-lidar~~ and integrate their data into daily operations?

→ This is a typical
site operator challenge

The results

These are not wind lidar problems.

The results

These are not wind lidar problems.
These are commercial(isation) problems.

We are in a valley of death for commercialisation

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Valley of death:

Not every problem needs a solution.

Not every solution finds a customer.

Some problems go away themselves.

Key challenges

- Privacy and security concerns
- Cost of solutions / unclear ROI
- Lack of knowledge about solutions
- Lack of standards and interoperability concerns
- Uncertainty that the technology will deliver promised benefits
- Poorly defined workflows and immature technology
- Reluctance to share data and concerns around competition

The importance of interoperability

- Digital products form part of a process chain
- New products require users to adapt their processes
- ... so new products are easier to introduce in growing markets

What about common data formats?

What about common data formats?

They work. They just need to be adopted.

Closing

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Lessons learned:

- **No digitalisation challenges** unique to wind lidar
- **Lots of commercial(isation) challenges**
- **Look outside of the wind energy industry**, e.g. smartphones and IoT
- **Be open about your needs**
- **Task 52 can be a forum** for new technologies to meet users, but can't push commercialisation if the need is not there.

Coming Q4 2025:

- **Report** documenting use cases and our perspectives

Lessons learned:

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Coming Q4 2025

- **Report** documenting use cases and our perspectives

Show of hands:
Would you join a monthly "pitch" about a new digital solution for wind lidar, e.g. from a startup?

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